

Galaxy Evolution with Deep HST and Ground-based Surveys

Christopher J. Conselice

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How do we explore galaxy evolution in the distant Universe?

Ground = wide+shallow

Hubble=deep+narrow

By using both deep but small area Hubble and wide but shallow ground based surveys

UKIRT (Hawaii)

Hubble Space Telescope (HST)

ESO VISTA (Chile)

Combining both space and ground based optical/NIR telescopes is a powerful combination

The morphological evolution of galaxies

Note that visually determined disks are a very small fraction at $z > 2$
Peculiar galaxies dominate the population

For $\log M > 10$ systems

Mortlock, CC et al. (2015), Huertas-Company+15

Galaxies in the
2nd half of the
Universe's history

Galaxies in the
1st half of the
Universe's history

Key goal for galaxy formation studies is role of merging

Are these peculiars mergers?

Major mergers – measure with structure

Conselice+09

Bluck+12

Lotz+11

Mergers evolve as $(1+z)^{1-3}$ to $z = 3$

Hypothesis that mergers are involved

REFINE

(Redshift Evolution and Formation in Extragalactic Systems)

An analysis of redshifts and stellar masses for the three IR deep fields:

Ultra-VISTA: $K = 23.4$, 1.6 sq. degree

UDS: $K = 24.2$, 0.77 sq. degree

VIDEO: $K = 22.5$, 1 sq. degree

GAMA: 144 sq. degree (nearby uni)

Useful for $z < 3$ – large volume

The different surveys probe different parts of the universe's history

CANDELS

REFINE

Image modified from an original by NASA/WMAP Science Team

For higher redshifts up to $z = 6$

Duncan, CC+19
Mundy, CC+17

See an increase up to $z = 6$ in CANDELS and REFINE

Fitting forms – power-law and power-law/exponential

Mass Bin	f_0	m	τ	s	BIC
Power-law					
$9.7 < \log_{10} M_{\star} < 10.3$	$0.024^{+0.005}_{-0.004}$	$1.775^{+0.205}_{-0.196}$	-	$0.009^{+0.100}_{-0.009}$	-121.5
$\log_{10} M_{\star} > 10.3$	$0.032^{+0.009}_{-0.007}$	$0.844^{+0.216}_{-0.235}$	-	$0.002^{+0.036}_{-0.002}$	-218.1
Power-law + Exponential					
$9.7 < \log_{10} M_{\star} < 10.3$	$0.030^{+0.009}_{-0.007}$	$4.431^{+1.721}_{-1.590}$	$-1.028^{+0.621}_{-0.672}$	$0.010^{+0.094}_{-0.010}$	-120.2
$\log_{10} M_{\star} > 10.3$	$0.033^{+0.008}_{-0.007}$	$0.439^{+1.085}_{-0.939}$	$0.131^{+0.291}_{-0.363}$	$0.001^{+0.024}_{-0.001}$	-214.7

$$f_m = f_0 \times (1 + z)^m$$

$m = 1-2$ in value – slightly lower than previous work

Merger rates, harder to infer – need time-scales

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{merg}}(z) = \frac{f_{\text{merg}}(z)}{\langle T_{\text{obs}} \rangle}, \quad [\text{Gyr}^{-1}]$$

Caveat

We use an evolving time-scale for mergers such that they have shorter time-scales at higher z , based on Illustris simulation

$$\Gamma_{\text{merg}}(z) = \frac{\phi_{\text{merg}}(z)}{\langle T_{\text{obs}} \rangle} = \frac{f_{\text{merg}}(z)n_1(z)}{\langle T_{\text{obs}} \rangle}, \quad [\text{Mpc}^{-3} \text{Gyr}^{-1}]$$

Gives ~ 1 major merger per galaxy at $z < 3$

Can compare with star formation history

The mass accretion rate due to major mergers

The mass accretion rate only becomes similar to the sSFR At $z > 4$

Star formation is the dominate process for forming galaxy stellar mass until $z > 4$

However, does not include induced SF by mergers

Merger rates consistent with a deep machine learning approach

CANDELS galaxies trained with Illustris TNG300

Merger rates consistent with a deep machine learning approach

Ferreira, CC+2019, in prep

Also indications for this in the size evolution of galaxies

Outer radius grows faster than inner radius – inside out formation

Whitney, CC+19, submitted

Where do all the baryons come from to produce star formation?

Gas mass fractions – too low to sustain SF

How much gas do we need beyond what mergers bring? (argument from Conselice+2013)

$$M_*(t) = M_*(0) + M_{*,M}(t) + \langle \psi \rangle \delta t$$

Stellar mass evolution

$$M_g(t) = M_g(0) + M_{g,M}(t) + M_{g,A}(t) - \langle \psi \rangle \delta t$$

Gas mass evolution

$$\frac{M_g(t)}{M_*(t)} \sim \frac{M_g(0)}{M_*(0)}$$

Observed condition

$$M_{g,A}(t) = (1.18 \pm 0.21) \times M_g(0) + \langle \psi \rangle \delta t - M_{g,M}(t)$$

Amount of
gas accreted

Integrate: Mass added from SF \sim Mass added from major merging
However - gas mass fraction for $\log M > 11$ is less than 0.2

The amount of gas added from accretion (or very minor mergers)

$$M_{g,A}(t) = (1.18 \pm 0.21) \times M_g(0) + \langle \psi \rangle \delta t - M_{g,M}(t)$$

$$\frac{M_{g,A}(t)}{M_*} = \frac{(1.18 \pm 0.21) \times M_g(0)}{M_*} + \frac{\langle \psi \rangle \delta t}{M_*} - \frac{M_{g,M}(t)}{M_*}$$

$$M_{g,A}/M_*(0) = 0.83 \pm 0.37$$

Over $1.5 < z < 3$ (2.16 Gyr)

$$(1.6 \pm 0.5) \times 10^{11} M_\odot$$

Average amount of gas accreted

Results in accretion rate of $\frac{dM_{g,A}(t)}{dt} = \dot{M}_{g,A} = (83 \pm 36) M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$

Gas accretion rate history for massive systems over cosmic time

Owensworth, CC+15

Decline due to galaxy quenching?

Merger Rate Densities

Merger rate densities give us the number of galaxies merging per unit volume – perhaps the most ‘physical’ measurement we can make with mergers

$$\Gamma_{\text{merg}}(z) = \frac{\phi_{\text{merg}}(z)}{\langle T_{\text{obs}} \rangle} = \frac{f_{\text{merg}}(z)n_1(z)}{\langle T_{\text{obs}} \rangle}, \quad [\text{Mpc}^{-3} \text{ Gyr}^{-1}]$$

Merger history out to $z=15$ – major implications for gravitational waves
Galaxy mergers will produce low frequency grav. waves

LISA – Most sensitive to supermassive black holes mergers at $z > 3$ – predict one a year at $z > 6$

Pulsar timing arrays can be used to measure the gravitational wave background due to mergers of SMBHs up to $z = 3$

How do galaxy mergers produce gravitational waves?

The cumulative number of mergers
LISA will find from known mergers
of galaxies from Duncan+18 results
About 1 a year!

Prediction based on galaxy
mergers for the h_c values for
pulsar timing arrays

Chen, Sesana, Conselice (2018)
arXiv:1810.04184

Minor Merger Pair Fraction - ratio $> 1/10$

Minor mergers are thought by some MORE important for mass assembly than major mergers. Should be more common.

What about even high redshifts?

Mass functions a good guide : Duncan, CC+2014

Before JWST – We must use Hubble Frontier Fields

But, very difficult to do!

GALFIT Model

GALFIT Model

GALFIT Residual

Want to go deeper and to higher redshifts – Frontier Fields

Frontier Field object MACS J0416.1-2403

Fitting and subtracting the giant galaxies

Rachana Bhatawdekar, CC+18

Results: UV Luminosity Function

$Z=6,7,8,9$ LF – steep and agrees with previous work

Rachana Bhatawdekar, CC+19

Mass function is very steep at highest redshifts

$Z=6,7,8,9$ Mass functions – *no obvious turn over* and very steep

Rachana Bhatawdekar, CC+19

First measurement of stellar mass density at $z \sim 9$

Significant amount of mass at $z \sim 9$

Rachana Bhatawdekar, CC+19

Is there enough star formation to create so much mass?

Very steep SF drop at $z > 9$, not enough time to create all the mass at $z=9$

This is a possible “Star Formation Catastrophe”

The future

James Webb Space Telescope (JWST)
deep and small fields

Euclid – wide

Leading JWST programmes and the Legacy Science lead for Euclid

The Clio Cluster: JWST target for lensing

Selection of JWST cluster lenses-probe the very earliest galaxies

A. Griffiths+CC and Webb Medium Deep Fields JWST IDS GTO

Clio cluster– less Intracluster light – more typical environments

Clio FORS2 imaging

Clio Cluster ESO VLT/MUSE spectroscopy

Already finding
several $z > 5$ galaxies
with modest
exposure times

JWST GTO Target

ERC EPOCHS –
Post-docs needed!

Euclid Wide and Deep Surveys probe unique parameter space

The equivalent 5 year Wide and Deep surveys would take ~700 and 72 years, respectively, to carry out with VISTA

Automation is important – however, must be tested in detail

Summary

1. Galaxy formation and evolution are driven by mergers in part, but their role is just being quantitatively revealed
2. There are major and minor mergers in galaxies up to $z=3$.
Not the dominant method for formation, but still important at the 25-50% level. Could be higher if merger time-scale evolves.
3. Mergers are relatively more important for galaxy formation at late and early times, whereby at 'mid' times star formation is a factor of ~ 5 more important at $z \sim 2$
4. Can measure merger history at $3 < z < 6$ – higher than at lower redshifts – important for LISA GW preparations
5. JWST will probe the earliest galaxies to determine how they and the first stars formed